

INTERFACIAL EVALUATION OF CARBON FIBER/CNT-PHENOLIC COMPOSITES BY DUAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted a good deal of interest due to their unique one-dimensional structures and novel properties [1,2]. The outstanding intrinsic mechanical properties of CNTs have resulted in considerable attention in their use as the reinforcement in composite materials. Although CNTs exhibit remarkable mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties, owing to their unique structures, their surface inertness has been a substantial obstacle to their usage in composites for many scientific and industrial applications. Incorporation of functional groups on the surface of CNTs has been one of the aspects for CNT research and has been actively studied, employing wet chemical methods, such as covalent approaches, defect site chemistry and noncovalent interactions [3-5].

Recently, studies in which plasma treatment (a solvent-free dry process), have been used to modify the CNT surface. Various functional groups have been incorporated onto the CNT surface by exposure to reactive gases under a glow discharge [6-9]. Plasma treatment modifies the uppermost atomic layers of a material's surface without significantly affecting its bulk properties.

The increasing importance of phenolic composites for many applications makes the accurate determination of mechanical properties an important endeavor. The addition of a CNT network to a phenolic matrix significantly improves the mechanical properties of CNT-phenolic composites [10]. Due to their high specific stiffness and strength accompanied by outstanding fatigue performance, carbon fiber reinforced phenolic composites are finding uses in a variety of industries, notably aerospace and transportation. Strong and durable interfacial adhesion is needed to effectively transfer stresses from the phenolic matrix to the fibers,

resulting in good mechanical performance of a composite [11-14].

A single fiber fragmentation test had been developed and used as an effective method to investigate interfacial shear strength (IFSS) [15]. In such tests the failure-elongation of the matrix should be several times larger than the fiber to result in a "saturated fragmentation state". Phenolic resins are rather difficult matrices on which to apply conventional fragmentation tests because of their brittle nature and high modulus. To help alleviate this problem the dual matrix (DMC) specimen has been developed as a modification of the single fiber composite (SFC) [16]. A DMC specimen is composed of a single fiber, with a brittle inner matrix supported by a ductile surrounding outer matrix. When this specimen is subjected to a slowly increasing transfer loading some fragmentation of the embedded fiber typically results before failure of brittle inner matrix.

Acoustic emission (AE) is recognized as an important nondestructive testing (NDT) method. It has been used as a valuable and reliable tool for the characterization of the structural integrity and to help identify the damage mechanisms for complex material systems and structures, subjected to various loading conditions [17,18]. In continuous fiber reinforced composites, the fracture of fibers has been found to be strongly correlated to the final failure of the composite structural components. For these complex materials, it has been shown that the integrity of the reinforcing phase largely determines the capability of the internal micro-structure to withstand the external loads. The ability to identify and to quantify the failure of reinforcing fibers during the loading process should provide valuable information for optimizing strength and predicting the integrity/life of a macro-structure.

In this work, air plasma treatment of CNT surfaces was performed to incorporate functional groups on

the surface of CNTs. Such functional groups are very useful as anchoring sites for binding other materials. To evaluate the interfacial properties between carbon fiber and CNT-phenolic composites, the apparent IFSS between fibers and matrix were determined by dual matrix and AE tests.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Carbon fiber (T700S, Toray Inc., Japan), with an average diameter of approximately 8 μm , was used as the reinforcing fiber. Multi-wall carbon nanotube (CNT, IJIn Nantech Co., Korea) was used as reinforcing and self-sensing material. Phenolic resin (RESINOX SC-1008, Monsanto Chemical Co., U.S.A.) based on a phenolic resole resin was used as the composite matrix.

2.2 Plasma treatment of CNT

Fig.1. Schematic of plasma treatment on CNT

An atmospheric pressure plasma apparatus, (RPS50, UION Co., Ltd., Korea), was used for treating the CNT. An electrode design in the device was employed to produce a stable discharge at 20 kHz frequency at atmospheric pressure, and at a power setting of—at 400 W. Fig. 1 shows a schematic diagram for the plasma treatment on CNT. Distilled water was used as the dispersion solvent as well as the medium for plasma treatment of the CNTs in a Petri dish. This treatment method was used because of the light weight nature of the fine-powdered CNTs which otherwise would not remain stable under the plasma radiation. As noted in figure one the plasma treatment process started with (1) 2 hours

sonication of a mixture of CNT and water to obtain a uniform dispersion, (2) transfer of this dispersion to a Petri dish, (3) ½ to 2 minute relatively uniform plasma radiation treatment and (4) concluding with a 24 hour evaporation/drying process at 60°C to remove the liquid.

The CNT surfaces experienced morphological changes during the plasma treatment which were analyzed by FT-IR. The wettability of CNT, after plasma treatment was, determined by static contact angle measurement of water droplets placed on a CNT coated surface. The specimens used for the contact angle measurements were prepared as follows. Glass plates, pre-cleaned with ethanol and the sonically treated in double distilled water were used as the substrates. The CNT coating was applied to these plates by spray coating with a 0.05 wt% CNT suspension using nitrogen gas as the carrier. At the end of the coating process the specimens were dried, in a clean oven at 60°C, to remove any solvent. This water drop measurement is based on the fact that the surface area for water droplets on a surface is minimized due to the surface tensions resulting from intermolecular forces.

2.3 Fabrication of dual matrix composites

Fig.2. Schematic sketch of dual matrix specimen

Fig. 2 shows schematically the DMC specimens used for the damage sensing tests. These specimens were composed of a single carbon fiber, a brittle inner layer (CNT-phenolic composite) and a ductile outside matrix (epoxy matrix). Dual matrix tests were performed to sense the fiber breakage inside the conductive inner matrix (the CNT-phenolic) as the specimen is loaded in tension. For deposition of

the CNT-phenolic composite on the carbon fiber the phenolic resin was first diluted with an acetone solvent by mechanical mixing. The CNT was then dispersed in the phenolic solution by sonication in a sealed beaker for 8 hours. Next the dispersive solvent was evaporated under sonication for 12 hours. While several concentrations of CNT in the CNT-phenolic composites were investigated in the previous studies, the concentration in this study was conducted only at 0.3 vol%. After deposition of the composite on the fiber, the curing process involved 3 temperature steps: 70 °C for 1.5 hours, then 100 °C for 1 hour, and then 140 °C for 4 hours, all in an autoclave at a pressure of 100 psi.

2.4 Dual matrix fragmentation test

To model the progression of the carbon fiber breaks with stress in dual matrix fragmentation test, the flaws with strength less than or equal to σ are divided into two categories: flaws which cause breaks, and flaws which lie within the load recovery regions of breaks and are thus obscured [19]. This situation is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Representation of flaws within a single fiber

When a single carbon fiber is embedded in a matrix, and a steadily increasing uniaxial stress is applied, the fiber breaks at its weakest point (largest flaw) and there is a transfer of load to the surrounding matrix, as shown schematically in Fig. 3(b). When a fiber breaks, the axial stress carried by the fiber at the break point is zero, and the load is transferred to the surrounding matrix by the shear stress that emerges at the interface between the fiber and the matrix. On the other hand the axial load now carried by the fiber increases from zero, at a fiber break, until it reaches a constant stress (called far-field stress) at a certain distance from the fiber break. The length of this zone, where the stress is smaller than the far-field value, is called the load recovery region. As the number of breaks increases, some flaws will be “obscured” in the load recovery region, as shown in Fig. 3(c).

The critical fragment length was originally described by Kelly-Tyson [20], and it has been rather generally used to estimate IFSS from the fiber fragmentation test. Equation 1 is based on the basis assumption that all fragments in saturation are debonded or the nearby matrix has yielded to provide for a constant shear stress at the interface and the IFSS τ is given by:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2L_c} \quad (1)$$

2.5 AE measurement

The DMC specimens for measuring AE parameters and electrical resistance were tested using an AE device (MISTRAS 2001 System, Physical Acoustic Co.USA) and a mini-UTM (Pico Industrial Inc., Korea) with a 100 kg load cell at a test speed of 0.5 mm/minute. The change in electrical resistance associated with fiber breakage and the deformation of CNT composites were measured and correlated with the AE parameters. That is, to evaluate the microfailure mechanisms occurring within the composite materials, AE tests were used in combination with micromechanical tests.

AE signals were obtained using a miniature sensor (Wide band, WD model, Physical Acoustics Co., USA) with a peak sensitivity of 55 Ref. V/(m/s) [62.5 Ref. V/mbar] and resonant frequency of 125 [650] kHz. The sensor output was amplified by 40 dB by a preamplifier and passed through a band-pass filter with a range of 100–1000 kHz with the threshold level set as 40 dB. A wide band PZT sensor was fixed to the center of the DMC. The signals from elastic waves occurring from microfailure were detected and converted to voltage signals by the PZT sensor, and then to AE parameters. A frequency analysis of the waveforms, by fast *Fourier* transform (FFT), was used to identify the characteristic peaks of the frequency components for the failure sources.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 IR and wettability analysis of CNT

Fig.4. FTIR-spectra of plasma treated CNT

To investigate possible changes in chemical composition at the surface of the CNT, the CNT was bombarded with air-plasma at 400 W for 10 sec on which FT-IR spectroscopy measurements in the mid infrared (4000-500cm⁻¹) were performed. As shown in Fig.4, the stretching vibration of O-H at 3590cm⁻¹, the stretching vibration of C-O at 1300cm⁻¹ and the C=O stretching vibration peak at 1750cm⁻¹ had a higher intensity after plasma treatment than originally, indicating that the CNTs had been oxidized and etched by the plasma treatment. It is inferred from this that many active chemical groups are produced on the surface of the CNTs which will likely lead to improved interfacial adhesion and to better reinforcement.

Fig.5. Static contact angle of plasma treated CNT

Fig. 5 shows photographs of water droplets used for static contact angle measurement for the plasma treated CNT as different treatment times. The diameters of the water droplets are in the 1 mm range. From these photographs one may conclude that CNTs become significantly more hydrophilic plasma treatment. The water droplet on untreated CNT coating exhibits a contact angle of approximately 120 degrees. The contact angle decreased significantly during the first minute of plasma treatment but during the next minute of treatment the contact angle decreased only slightly. Apparently the wettability of the CNTs does not increase proportionate with the treatment time when this threshold is exceeded. Therefore, only CNTs

with 1 minute plasma treatment were investigated in the other parts of this study (as which was selected as a sort of optimal treatment time).

3.2 Comparison of apparent IFSS

The interfacial properties of carbon fiber/CNT-phenolic composites were further investigated, using fragmentation tests as shown in Fig. 5. The morphology associated with the fiber breaks can offer valuable clues regarding the interface shear strength. Fig. 6(a) shows an amplified picture of carbon fiber breaks in phenolic DMC. Significant interface debonding was not observed for the phenolic DMC containing carbon fiber. The failure of the phenolic matrix indicated a relatively strong interface bond, with a mixture of break widening and apparent local deformation of the matrix. Fig. 6(b) and (c) show the matrix cracks of phenolic and CNT-phenolic matrix, respectively. Failure of epoxy outside matrix was also observed with the inner matrix crack, implying a reasonably effective supportable interface.

Fig.6. Polarized graph of fiber breaks

3.3 Nondestructive AE damage sensing

Fig.7. Damage sensing for phenolic DMC

Fig. 7 shows the results for phenolic DMC: (a) without a carbon fiber; (b) with a carbon fiber. The figures show Stress, AE Amplitude, AE Energy and Electrical Resistance for the indicated specimens as a function of applied strain. There were no electrical resistivity results in Fig. 7(a), due to the absence of a carbon fiber. Fig. 7(b) shows the results for a specimen with a carbon fiber. In this case there was initially a finite resistance but when the first fiber break occurred, the electrical resistivity increased infinitely because the phenolic matrix was an electrical insulator.

Fig. 8 shows waveforms and their FFT analysis for the damage sensing of a carbon fiber and a phenolic matrix by AE: (a) carbon fiber break; (b) phenolic matrix crack. Typical the waveforms for carbon fiber breaks were observed to have smaller amplitudes than the waveforms for cracking in the phenolic matrix. The FFT patterns of carbon fiber breaks were also significantly different from those for phenolic matrix cracks.

Fig.8. Waveforms and their FFT analysis

Damage sensing results for plasma treated CNT-phenolic composites are shown in Fig. 9. Because of the conductive CNT-phenolic composites, the measured electrical resistivity for the CNT-phenolic composites matrix specimen was finite even in the absence of a carbon fiber, as shown in Fig. 9(a), but the electrical resistivity increased infinitely at the occurrence of the first matrix crack. The three sets of AE signals resulted from cracks in the CNT-phenolic matrix. The results for the carbon fiber reinforced CNT-phenolic DMC specimen, shown in Fig. 9(b), were rather different. In this case, fiber

breakage could be detected simultaneously by measurement in changes in electrical resistivity as well as AE measurement. Electrical resistivity increased stepwise with progressing fiber break but remained finite due to maintenance of electrical conductivity by the conductive CNT-phenolic matrix. As a consequence, the electrical resistivity remained essential constant until the first carbon fiber break, after which the electrical resistivity increased gradually and continuously until it suddenly increased to essentially infinity when the initial crack of the CNT-phenolic matrix occurred.

Fig.9. Damage sensing for CNT-phenolic DMC

Fig. 10 shows waveforms and their FFT analysis for the damage sensing of carbon fiber and plasma treated CNT-phenolic composites by AE: (a) a carbon fiber break; (b) a CNT-phenolic composites crack. Characteristic peaks of carbon fiber break in the CNT-phenolic were similar to that for BMC in Fig. 8(a), while the waveforms of CNT-phenolic composites crack exhibited significantly larger amplitudes than those for phenolic matrix cracks. This latter effect is attributed to the improved

adhesion resulting from the plasma treatment of the CNTs.

Fig.10. Waveforms and their FFT analysis

4 Conclusions

This paper reports on an investigation of a novel process of atmospheric pressure plasma treatment. This is an easy, rapid, and effective way of functionalizing the surface of powder CNTs using water as a dispersion solvent for the plasma treatment. FT-IR analysis indicates that this treatment primarily creates oxygen containing groups on the CNT surface. Static contact angle measurement showed that the treatment significantly

improved the wettability of the CNTs and that the most sizeable changes occurred in the first minute of plasma treatment. During tensile loading of DMC specimens, electrical resistance increased stepwise upon progressing carbon fiber breakage. This is due to the fact that while a break in the carbon fiber does interrupt the continuity of flow in the fiber per se the remaining parts of the CNT network in contact with the fiber constitutes effective current bridges around the breaks. The shorter critical break length of the carbon fiber for plasma treated CNT-phenolic composite specimens provides additional evidence for the effectiveness of the plasma treatment for increasing the IFSS between the fiber and this matrix.

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References

- [1] S. Iijima "Helical microtubules of graphitic carbon". *Nature*, Vol. 354, pp. 28–56, 1991.
- [2] B.I. Yakobson, C.J. Brabec and J. Bernholc "Nanomechanics of carbon tubes: instabilities beyond linear response". *Phys Rev Lett*, Vol. 76, pp. 2511–2514, 1996.
- [3] D. Tasis, N. Tagmatarchis, A. Bianco and M. Prato "Chemistry of carbon nanotubes". *Chemical Reviews*, Vol. 106, pp. 1105–1136, 2006.
- [4] J.L. Bahr, J. Yang, D.V. Kosynkin, M.J. Bronikowski, R.E. Smalley and J.M. Tour "Functionalization of carbon nanotubes by electrochemical reduction of aryl diazonium salts: a bucky paper electrode". *J Am Chem Soc*, Vol. 123, pp. 6536–6542, 2001.
- [5] K. Balasubramanian and M. Burghard "Chemically functionalized carbon nanotubes". *Small*, Vol. 1, pp. 180–192, 2005.
- [6] Q. Chen, L. Dai, M. Gao, S. Huang and A. Mau "Plasma activation of carbon nanotubes for chemical modification". *J Phys Chem B*, Vol. 105, pp. 618–622, 2001.
- [7] T. Xu, J. Yang, J. Liu and Q. Fu "Surface modification of multi-walled carbon nanotubes by O₂ plasma". *Appl Surf Sci*, Vol. 253, pp. 8945–8951, 2007.
- [8] J.G. Jones, A.R. Waite, C. Muratore and A.A. Voevodin "Nitrogen and hydrogen plasma treatment

- of multi-walled carbon nanotubes". *J Vac Sci Technol B*, Vol. 26, pp. 995–1000, 2008.
- [9] L. Valentini, D. Puglia, F. Carniato, E. Boccaleri, L. Marchese and J.M. Kenny "Use of plasma fluorinated single-walled carbon nanotubes for the preparation of nanocomposites with epoxy matrix". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 68, pp. 1008–1014, 2008.
- [10] M. Yeh, N. Tai and J. Liu "Mechanical behavior of phenolic-based composites reinforced with multi-walled carbon nanotubes". *Carbon*, Vol. 44, pp. 1–9, 2006.
- [11] S.J. Park and Y.S. Jang "Interfacial characteristics and fracture toughness of electrolytically Ni-plated carbon-fiber-reinforced phenolic resin matrix composites". *J Coll Inte Sci*, Vol. 237, pp. 91–97, 2001.
- [12] M.H. Choi, B.H. Jeon and I.J. Chung "The effect of coupling agent on electrical and mechanical properties of carbon fiber/phenolic resin composites". *Polymer*, Vol. 41, pp. 3243–3252, 2000.
- [13] A. Pegoretti and T. Ricco "Crack growth in discontinuous glass fibre reinforced polypropylene under dynamic and static loading conditions". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 33, pp. 1539–1547, 2002.
- [14] J.M. Park, Z.J. Wang, J.H. Jang, N.J.R. Gnidakoung, W.I. Lee, J.G. Park and K.L. DeVries "Interfacial and hydrophobic evaluation of glass fiber/CNT-epoxy nanocomposites using electro-micromechanical technique and wettability test". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 40, pp. 1722–1731, 2009.
- [15] J.M. Park, J.W. Kim and D.J. Yoon "Interfacial evaluation and microfailure mechanisms of single carbon fiber/bismaleimide (BMI) composites by tensile and compressive fragmentation tests and acoustic emission". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 62(6), pp. 743–756, 2002.
- [16] S.I. Lee, J.M. Park, D.W. Shin and D.J. Yoon "Interfacial properties of glass fiber/brittle-ductile dual matrix composites using micro-mechanical techniques and acoustic emission". *Polym Comp*, Vol. 20, pp. 19–28, 1999.
- [17] R.K. Verma, R.G. Kander and B.S. Hsiao "Acoustic emission monitoring of damage using high amplitude gains in carbon fiber reinforced poly(etheretherketone)". *J Mater Sci Lett*, Vol. 13, pp. 438–442, 1994.
- [18] B.T. Ma, L.S. Schadler, C. Laird and J.C. Figueroa "Acoustic emission in single filament carbon/polycarbonate and Kevlar/polycarbonate composite under tensile deformation". *Polym Compos*, Vol. 11, pp. 211–216, 1990.
- [19] R. Gulino and S.L. Phoenix "Weibull strength statistics for graphite fibres measured from the break progression in a model graphite/glass/epoxy microcomposite". *J Mater Sci*, Vol. 26, pp. 3107–3118, 1991.
- [20] T.H. Jung, R.V. Subramanian and V.S. Manoranjan "Prediction of fibre strength at the critical length: a simulation theory and experimental verification for bimodally distributed carbon fibre strengths". *J Mater Sci*, Vol. 28, pp. 4489–4496, 1993.